

TRANSFORMING THE YORKSHIRE FOOD SYSTEM FOR PEOPLE AND PLANET

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Yorkshire is the largest county in England with a high diversity of soils, land cover and farming systems, and the highest concentration of food and drink businesses in the UK.

Our Yorkshire food system includes production to consumption and everything in between. It provides important sustenance and supports our economies in Yorkshire, but the way food is produced and consumed also causes major harm to our environment and people's health.

We urgently need to transform to a different kind of fair and just food system that is regenerative, where human activities and ecosystem processes mutually reinforce one another and enhance the wellbeing of people and our planet.

Three Horizons map of core findings

Using the powerful Three Horizons futures process, FixOurFood captured 1400 insights from 113 different experts from 55 organisations through surveys and workshops about challenges in the present, desired future food systems and how transformation can be supported.

Here are our initial findings.

Challenges and envisioned future

The current Yorkshire food system is dominated by large producers and retailers, lacks resilience, and provides limited opportunity for local agency and innovation. The primary focus is on efficiency, price, convenience and yield, and biodiversity and soil quality are declining. Many people don't have access to healthy food. The current food system reinforces social inequalities, feeds climate change, and is degenerative, threatening the health of people and the planet.

In contrast, our desired future food system is diverse, resilient, and well connected, with extensive local engagement, high self-sufficiency, and with people feeling empowered. It is one that prioritises environmental regeneration and provides healthy nutrition and economies.

Regenerative farming would be thriving, and the system would have a strong connection between people, their food and where food comes from.

Core contrasts between the current and envisioned future food system

Current system	Envisioned system
Low diversity	High diversity
Healthy and sustainable food for the few	Healthy and sustainable food is universal
Concentrated power	Distributed power
Actors work in isolation	Actors work through networks, cooperation, sharing
Farming focused on maximising yield	Farming focused on improving livelihoods and resilience
Consumers expect huge freedom of food choice	Consumers embrace opportunities of seasonality, more local sourcing
Focus on price, efficiency and convenience	Focus on environmental and human health
Limited view of food: Nutrition and fuel	Holistic view of food: Nutrition, culture, social engagement, community, health, education and environment

Supporting a transformational pattern shift

Getting to the envisioned food system will be challenging. But there are many examples of producers, networks, and organisations – the pockets of the future envisioned system in the present – who are already doing things differently. The challenge is then learning how to connect and scale innovations, disrupt the status quo, and create space for a regenerative Yorkshire food system to emerge.

Five important areas of action that have been identified that will help to disrupt and support system change are:

- 1. Enhance supply chain connectivity and innovation.** New supply chain platforms and networks of hybrid businesses that have a focus on environmental and social benefits beyond profit need to be established and strengthened. Supply chains need to be reconfigured to support more direct sales, local and seasonal sourcing, and enhance connections between producers and consumers. Dynamic platforms are also needed so large procurers (schools, hospitals etc) can access locally and sustainably produced food. Strategic action to attract necessary funding and capital will be needed to support such platforms, as well as ensuring the purchasing of food is easy for all and that excessive value is not siphoned off by platform providers.
- 2. Rapidly scale environmentally beneficial farming.** This requires long-term policy and market support and stronger market incentives. Long-term commitment across the region for support is needed via city and regional-scale councils, partnerships and networks, as well as in national policy working to ensure subsidy schemes, such as ELMS and carbon credits, genuinely provide appropriate levels of support for new forms of production.

Getting large-scale food producers on board, changing education around food, and giving greater recognition to regenerative farming (e.g. designating 'Areas of Outstanding Natural Farming'), while also helping farmers navigate funding schemes will be important. Better evidence of the benefits of regenerative farming methods will also be required.

- 3. Empower consumer demand towards the purchase of regeneratively produced food.** The public need to be inspired to lead a culture change in what they buy and eat, shifting emphasis to locally and seasonally produced food. By building on the many exemplar groups and organisations working in schools and early years settings that are already changing consumer mindsets – such as TastEd, Rethink Food, and Chefs in Schools, to name a few – food literacy of school staff, students and families can be improved. Use of urban space for food growing, twinning urban and rural farms, and strengthening linkages between people and where their food comes from will be important. Key to success will also be making regeneratively produced food affordable while generating decent income for producers, being sensitive to different motivations of those involved, providing physical infrastructure to support local purchasing, and providing good information to consumers about the health or environmental impact of food.
- 4. Provide trusted knowledge and support for new regenerative standards and incentives.** New policy will be needed to change standards and incentives that support the production of regeneratively produced food. This, in turn, needs to be complemented by provision of unbiased, respectful technological and scientific knowledge to farmers about how best to farm regeneratively. New standardised indicators and tools will also help compare effectiveness of practices and their outcomes from different areas and operating at different geographical scales. There are opportunities to build on those already doing this, such as Soil Benchmark who help farmers maximise use of their soil data. Transparency about where data comes from and 'data ambassadors' in charge of sharing data are likely to be required.

5. **Support schools and young people as drivers of long-term change.**

Schools and young people are important drivers and advocates for change in the food system. Whole school approaches, such as growing food in school gardens and learning how to harvest and cook food, are particularly useful. These, in turn, need to be enabled through engagement with school leadership and the institutionalisation of whole school approaches through mandatory food standards and via food award schemes. Food security and accessibility of tasty, healthy food for all needs to be supported by free school meal auto-enrolment while involving students and parents/carers in school food decision-making, including menu co-design, can help motivate them to be champions of transformation. National level policy to support schools as drivers will be essential, especially given current limits of national funding. Finally, support is needed to change schools' contracting and procurement practices, and the budgets they have for procuring food, so schools can be a key focal point to support purchase of regeneratively produced food.

These five important areas of action will, together, stimulate a significant change in the Yorkshire food system if: (1) they are cohered so as to support each other mutually; (2) 'top-down' municipal, regional and national policy can enable more 'bottom-up' local-scale action; and (3) producer and consumer-led change are encouraged simultaneously. Maintaining ambition, celebrating successes, and strategically focusing on transformational change (not just change to improve the status quo) will also be important to encouraging system transformation towards a new kind of regenerative food future.

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This pamphlet was written by Sam Buckton and Ioan Fazey on behalf of FixOurFood.

FixOurFood is an ambitious research programme inspiring action across Yorkshire to co-create a regenerative food system. Underpinned by a robust evidence base, we are pioneering, envisioning, and stimulating respectful debate to drive transformation to ensure healthy people and a healthy planet.

You can find out more on our website fixourfood.org

To get in touch, please email fixourfood@york.ac.uk

